

SOCIOCULTURAL IDENTITY IN THE PROFESSIONAL MEDIA-EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Preservation of historical memory is an important task of higher education in the information age. The authors have made an attempt to overview of the notion «sociocultural identity» and emphasize the factors and conditions of its formation in the educational training of future journalists, advertising and public relations specialists. The category of sociocultural identity is considered within the framework of media-education as a unified process of training and education. The research has been conducted within the framework of competence and axiological approaches. Conceptuality, technology, predictability, and continuity are defined as key characteristics of professional education focused on the formation of sociocultural identity:

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Introduction

Today in the information society the dominant needs, ideas, meanings and concepts of a person are formed under the influence of the norms and rules system, which are broadcasted by mass media on a large scale. In adequate socio-political conditions, media discourse focuses on the cultural values of a certain society, stores and reproduces them, accumulating national memory.

Modern researchers formulate the actual «centaur-problem» of modern consciousness, within which the incongruous is combined. As a result, an ambivalent and chaotic picture of the world of a person who is capable of professing opposite attitudes and adhering to mutually exclusive judgments and values is massively observed [10]. Accordingly, the information space created and perceived in special conditions of psychic reality is radically changing. Modern media are able to transform social and cultural attitudes and perceptions of the audience. The instinct of national self-preservation is essentially human biology. Therefore the mental aggression of mass communication in this direction awakens the protective resources of the organism, turning into extreme forms of nationalism and chauvinism, which have become characteristic features of the last decade.

Results and discussions

Historical memory is organically connected with a person, his ethnic or national perception of himself and the surrounding reality. From the point of view of modern ethnopsychology, it is physically impossible to force an organism to have other ancestors and adopt a different cultural code. Moreover, it is cultural diversity that reveals the undoubted value of modern world civilization. The process of unification of the cultural and historical features of the society can be countered by

journalists' professional work with the constructs of national worldview.

Only when getting higher education students can not only acquire the necessary knowledge and skills, but also realize the cultural meanings of their professional activity. M. A. Voskresenskaya emphasizes that the problem of expanding sociocultural competencies in the professional training of future media specialists is highly relevant today and requires special attention. In the researcher's opinion, it is important to develop programs and courses that could not only increase the cultural erudition of future journalists, but also impart to them skills of journalistic analysis of the sociocultural functions of journalism [8].

Particular attention is paid to the concept of «identification». It is generally acknowledged that in science, this concept involves a comparison, correlation of an individual's ideals and values with the values that a particular society possesses and to which one must conform. According to I. A. Akimov, «Sociocultural identity is an individual's perception of himself as a member of a certain social and cultural group. Social identity is closely connected with the approval and acceptance of those values, norms, and ideals that are characteristic of it, when belonging to this or that sociocultural group acquires direct emotional significance for the individual himself» [1].

Researchers E. V. Savelova and M. A. Shermetiyeva consider sociocultural identity as the correlation of a person with society as a cultural and civilizational formation, which implies the adoption of a specific system of values by the individual [7]. In the process of socio-cultural identity formation, perceptions of oneself as relating to a certain type of culture and national mentality are formed. According to a number of authors, sociocultural identity covers the spiritual-psychological, political-legal and moral level of society. Socio-cultural identity is a way to establish its own civilizational specificity and originality. The key

semantic expression of eventuality is a person's awareness of his / her ethnic identity as a fragment of modern civilization [3]. Sociocultural identity of mass media representatives in modern studies is considered in the framework of national identification.

In his works M. P. Yatsenko calls historical memory the basis and guardian of socio-cultural identity in the era of globalization: «As a result of historical memory distortion, national cultures, which are an important basis of civilizational diversity of mankind, are gradually eliminated» [9]. The researcher gives us the impression that the devaluation of the established values of society is one of the greatest disasters of modern humanity.

The idea that the personal horizon of values is formed through the cultural norms of society, with which a person identifies himself, was put forward by I. A. Apollonov. According to the scientist, it is impossible to comprehend individual qualities of a person outside the socio-cultural context, since identity is a person's involvement into a certain culture, in the context of which the personal self-formation takes place [2].

In turn, it is the media that can be an effective material resource for the accumulation and dissemination of historical memory models. In this context, the sociocultural identity of a journalist is a complex socio-psychological phenomenon, which means that the journalist realizes and experiences his/her belonging to the spiritual and value paradigm of society, accepts and transmits the ideals, patterns of behavior, and cultural meanings of his/her native civilization in his/her work.

The purpose of our research is to analyze the essential characteristics of a journalist's sociocultural identity from the point of view of its actualization in the professional education of a journalist.

The research is conducted in the interdisciplinary field of pedagogy and psychology; axiological and cultural approaches are involved in emphasizing the values of national culture and the self-value of the individual. The analysis of the problem of the future journalists' sociocultural identity is based on the competence approach. The results of the higher education process in the direction of «Journalism» make up the focus of the researchers' attention and are as follows:

- the ability of graduates to act taking into account professional norms, values of society and a sense of responsibility for the results of their work;
- the ability to analyze the system of professional values, evaluate their own experience and continuously develop the necessary professional qualities.

In a complex geopolitical situation, modern journalism and advertising actively address the topic of mass identity, contextured from symbolic and iconic content and reflecting the specific cultural characteristics of society. The Characteristic examples of this are «*Analysis of Russian identity*» (NewsLand. 2014. October 19); «*Creation of the soul. In Tula region rural temples are being revived*» (AiF. 2023. October 2); «*We are different, but we are together*», the rubric «*Multifaceted Transbaikalia*» (Chita Obozrenie. 2022. November 16); «*Russianness should be done together*» (AiF. 2023. September 22); «*Achievements of creative*

industries representatives as a part of the festival «Soul of Russia» (Vedomosti.ru. 2023. May 4) and others. The process of saturating media discourse with fragments of the national picture of the world is not only a strategic task and a way of protection from outside influence, but also an opportunity to preserve its identity, «a special timbre in the symphonic orchestra of humanity» [5, p. 5].

Recognizing oneself as a part of the national community, belonging to a common civic position is a natural need of a human being as a social being. People living for a long time on the same territory acquire common concepts of worldview, reflected in reactions to socio-political events, in a set of family values, in a certain attitude to the native land and history, and even in the tools of self-development [6]. The complex process of actualization of the society's cultural meanings is manifested in sociocultural identity.

In the positively colored image of «I-professional» a person and profession form a single sociocultural whole, which is manifested in motivational and value, cognitive and behavioral components. Avdonina N. S. and Koytina D. S. explain that one of the central issues of the acquiring identity process is the adoption of values and value orientations. They state that cultural and moral values reflect the attitude of man to reality, determine the motives and goals of his professional activity [4].

Conclusion

Viewed in this light, the process of sociocultural identity development begins during the professional training of future journalists. The key parameters of this qualitative profile education are:

1) *Conceptuality*: journalist education implies assimilation of knowledge and views about the spiritual values of society as a coherent whole, represented by unique traditions, culture, and language; the ability formation to perceive the intercultural diversity of society in a socio-historical context.

A journalist student at a higher education institution must learn to think deeply, work independently and creatively, possessing the skills to cherish the linguistic cultural heritage, and understand the specifics of journalistic activity in socio-cultural realities.

2) *Handling properties*: mastering effective tools for objectifying cultural meanings in the space of a media text; developing the ability to use the diversity of achievements of national and world culture, as well as constructs of the national picture of the world in the process of creating media texts and media products of different genres and formats; mastering the technology of working with concepts, national stereotypes, narratives and archetypes when processing and interpreting texture.

3) *Predictability*: formation of the ability to evaluate and predict possible effects of one's own work, following the principles of social responsibility to society. Realization of the unchanging essence of a journalist's professional work, which is focused on supporting the country's social immunity, on awakening mental images and cultural values that are extremely important for the national identity of the society.

4) *Continuity*: creation of comfortable and necessary conditions for continuous improvement and realization of the self-development trajectory on the basis of the sociocultural code. The most important condition for the formation of sociocultural identity is the journalist's constant self-development and self-education, raising his or her cultural level and communicative skills.

There is every reason to identify the core competencies that demonstrate a journalist's sociocultural identity:

- understanding of journalism as a sociocultural phenomenon, as well as the value-orienting and culture-forming functions of the mass media;
- communicative competence taking into account the attitudes, needs, norms and values of society;
- skills of analyzing professional principles, norms and universal values;
- ability to perceive the intercultural diversity of society in socio-historical, ethical and philosophical contexts;
- the ability to create journalist texts for various media formats using the latest technologies on the basis of traditional values;
- competent and professional coverage of topical problems of modern society, taking into account its intercultural diversity, understanding their essence and causes;
- ability to interact effectively with the audience in the paradigm of mental representations of the society;
- formed sense of professional responsibility to the audience and colleagues for the results of his/her professional activity;
- being able to make a conscious and responsible choice of professional career, self-education, relationships on the basis of traditional values of the society.

On the basis of the research it is possible to conclude that in today's environment of value turbulence, the socio-cultural factor of media professional formation has become fundamental. The behavior of the author of media discourse should not be governed solely by situational and changeable needs. As has been mentioned earlier, it is values in their stability and emblematic meaning that act as one of the key elements of creativity. Sociocultural identity is a reflection of the national picture of the world of the author of a media text. These facts give rise to a conclusion that an important task of the pedagogical process is to actualize

sociocultural identity. This process requires further research in the field of the content and methodology of professional education.

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